

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report on the Training Materials
Deliverable D5.4**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D5.4

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

During ESiWACE3 training material has been developed. Two types of training material have been produced: (1) general material on the broad topic of high-performance computing in weather and climate which was mainly developed for the education of early career scientists and (2) teaching material on specific project-related topics that are covered in WP1-3, with the aim of transferring knowledge obtained in ESiWACE3 to a broader community. At the beginning of ESiWACE3, some related teaching material existed within the community. The key advances made during the reporting period are (1) to ensure the usefulness, usability and pedagogical quality of the material, the teaching material has been reviewed by pedagogical experts from the University of Helsinki and tested by small groups of students from the University of Helsinki and (2) the material has been gathered in an online repository, together with the pedagogical reviews, and will soon be published on the ESiWACE3 website thus making it accessible to the wider community.

2. Conclusion & Results

Training material was developed and reviewed by pedagogical experts in accordance with the ESiWACE3 grant agreement. The pedagogical reviews were found to improve the clarity of the material and to ensure that the summer schools were well designed with clear learning objectives that could be met by the planned learning activities. Recommendations for future summer schools were developed and are reported in this deliverable. The training material and the material for the pedagogical reviews have been collected together and will be published on the ESiWACE3 website. Currently they are available on the ESiWACE internal wiki pages:

<https://earth.bsc.es/esiwace3/doku.php?id=wiki:content:training>

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	yes
(2) Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	yes
(3) Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	no

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O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	no
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	no
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	no
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	yes
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Description of Training Material and their target audience

Three sets of training material were produced: material for two summer schools and kernel tuner training material.

Summer school 2024: This was organised by CSC and was reported on in ESiWACE2 D5.1. (2024). The material produced includes lecture slides and hands-on practical exercises. The target audience was advanced MSc students and PhD students in Atmospheric Sciences. The material was prepared by individual lectures / teachers from a number of different institutions. The lecture topics covered included: classical numerical modelling aspects, introduction to high performance computing, Earth system modelling, introduction to ICON, basics of MPI, OpenMP, MPI+OpenMP hybrid programming, basics of GPU programming, and lastly, novel concepts which including machine learning and AI approaches being used in weather and climate modelling. The hands-on practical sessions were designed to teach students how to visualise and analysis large datasets, including the use of healpix grids, and to gain experience in running ICON on the Levante HPC system.

Summer school 2025 “HPC4Climate”: This has been organised mainly by WarmWorld with input from ESiWACE3 partners. The material produced included lecture slides and material to guide students in “coding challenges”. The target audience differed somewhat from the 2024 summer school and was master students and early PhD students in computer science, data science, techno-mathematics, applied mathematics, meteorology, climate science with programming skills and an interest in scientific computing – hence there was more of a drive to attract students from outside of meteorology and climate science. Consequently, the topics covered in this summer school also differed from in 2024. The topics included introduction to the climate system and general circulation, basics of climate models, using GiT, parallel programming concepts, ICON including the ICON community Interface (Comin) and event detection and energy diagnostics in ICON. Through the guided coding challenges students have the change to run ICON experiments and modify aspects of the source code.

Kernel Tuner: Kernel Tuner is developed by ESiWACE3 as part of Work Package 2 Task 2.3 and is an easy-to-use software development tool for the creation of highly optimized and tuned GPU applications

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that are energy efficient. Training material on the use and applications of this software was produced. The target audience was advanced researchers already working in the field of HPC. The material was used as part of the online course “GPU optimization with Kernel Tuner” organised in September 2024 by the National Competence Centre for HPC Austria and ESiWACE3 with the aid of collaboration through CASTIEL2. Additionally, a tutorial was given at the Supercomputing Conference by ESiWACE3 researchers using this material. The training material consists of slides and Jupyter notebooks. The tutorial consists of several sections that interleave presentations and hands-on sessions. For these hands-on sessions several Jupyter notebooks that have been designed to run on Google Colab were used. This proved to be an excellent platform for giving instructor-led tutorials at conferences, as the participants do not have to access their GPU/HPC system from the conference.

4.2. Pedagogical Reviews

The teaching materials were reviewed by University of Helsinki employees, all of whom have completed at least 10 ECTS in pedagogical studies. The pedagogical reviewers were coordinated by Dr Victoria Sinclair who has extensive experience in designing and teaching courses in atmospheric sciences at university level and has taken 28 ECTS in university pedagogy. For the material for both summer schools, the pedagogical review consisted of experienced lecturers reviewing the material and small groups of advanced MSc and PhD students from the University of Helsinki working through the material. The MSc and PhD students focused on the clarity of the material and how well they could learn from the material. The experienced lecturers paid attention to how well two key aspects of higher education pedagogy were implemented: the concept of constructive alignment as proposed by Biggs (1996) and Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom et al., 1956; Bloom et al., 1964) a framework for categorizing different levels of objectives and skills that educators set for their students.

Constructive Alignment means that all components of the teaching and learning process are aligned with each other to support student learning. The central idea is to align the learning activities and assessment tasks with the intended learning outcomes (also referred to as learning objectives), ensuring that students are actively engaged in achieving those outcomes. This requires clear learning outcomes to be specified by the teacher and communicated to the students. In addition, how each learning activity (e.g., lecture, practical exercise, writing a report, giving a presentation etc) relates to which learning outcome needs to be considered and explained to students. Both sets of summer school material we reviewed were not constructively aligned as well as they could have been. This stems from (1) many different lecturers having prepared material and (2) there is no assessment to evaluate how well students have met the learning outcomes of the summer school. Both aspects are common to many summer schools and we make recommendations below on how to deal with these challenges.

Blooms taxonomy has a hierarchy of six levels, each representing a different type of cognitive skill: Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analysing, Evaluating and Creating. This framework encourages teachers to create learning objectives that encourage students to engage in higher-order thinking, moving beyond simple memorization to more complex cognitive processes – i.e., to move to the higher levels such as evaluating and creating knowledge. Overall, the summer school material covered a broad range of the 6 levels and certainly went beyond the basic levels of remembering and understanding. The practical exercises in the 2024 summer school enable students to apply their

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knowledge to new problems and analyse information by connecting different topics together. The coding challenges in the 2025 summer school are also very well designed as they enable students to create – they can take their knowledge, apply it and produce new code for the ICON model.

4.3. Recommendations for preparation of future training material

We have shown that pedagogical review is highly beneficial and can lead to notable enhancements in the overall design of summer schools and in the clarity of teaching material. Therefore, our main recommendation is that this exercise should be undertaken by all summer school organisers.

To ensure summer schools are constructively aligned, we recommend that learning outcomes are agreed between all contributing lecturers well in advance and are displayed on the course websites for students to see. In addition, we recommend that when preparing lectures and practical sessions, teachers should include a slide / text at the beginning stating what learning objectives will be addressed and at the end a slide / text stating what students should now know / have learnt.

To address the issue of no assessment in summer schools we recommend that compulsory feedback forms are sent to students which include questions where students are asked to self-assess how well they met the learning outcomes. We strongly recommend that the feedback forms are prepared well in advance of the course.

5. References

Biggs, John. (1996) "Enhancing teaching through constructive alignment." *Higher education* 32.3, 347-364.

Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill, W.H. and Krathwohl, D. R (1956) "A Taxonomy of Educational Objectives I, London: Longman.

Bloom, B. S., Krathwohl, D. R. and Masia, B. B. (1964). A Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, II. London: Longman.

ESiWACE2 D5.1. (2024). ESiWACE3 - Deliverable D5.1 - Report on the first summer school. <https://zenodo.org/records/14234261>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

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No notable changes were made. The main difficulty that was encountered was related to the timing of the pedagogical review relative to the training events. For effective and thorough pedagogical reviews to be performed, the material needs to be provided well in advance, ideally 2 months before the event. This is to enable the authors of the material to have sufficient time to make meaningful changes to the material. However, in terms of the summer schools, it has been challenging to receive complete and finalised material well in advance.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

Developing high quality, reusable training material contributes to the EuroHPC strategy by training a wide range of audiences in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use HPC environments in their research. Material has been developed for both early career scientists and more advanced researchers.

8. Sustainability

The approach taken in this deliverable to produce re-usable training material contributes to the sustainability of this. In addition, as most of the material can also be used as self-study material it is sustainable in the sense that students do not necessarily need to travel to specific events to benefit from the training material.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The training material will be made publicly available at the ESiWACE3 website.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached

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None

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

None

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None